

The InnoRenew CoE International Conference 2021

HEALTHY AND SUSTAINABLE
RENOVATION WITH
RENEWABLE MATERIALS

June 10-11 | Online

2021

**INNORENEW CoE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
2021**

ONLINE | 10-11 JUNE 2021

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

INNORENEW COE

Livade 6, 6310 Izola, Slovenia

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KEYNOTE ADDRESS

LISANNE HAVINGA, MSc. PHD

Assistant Professor Building Performance and Principal Scientist System Integration, Technische Universiteit Eindhoven

Lianne Havinga is Assistant Professor at the Building Performance group at Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) in the Netherlands. She is also Principal Scientist System Integration of the Eindhoven Institute for Renewable Energy Systems, and part of the management team of the institute. She received her Ph.D. in 2019 from TU/e, titled 'Advancing Post-War Housing: Integrating Heritage Impact, Environmental Impact, Hygrothermal Risk and Costs in Renovation Design Decisions'. Her research focuses on developing

modeling and simulation strategies to support decision-making in the energy transition of the built environment. Core topics include the optimization of renovation decisions using parametric exploration of housing variations, user behavior and renovation solutions. A holistic assessment of environmental impact, incorporating life cycle assessment and circularity, is a priority in her work. Lastly, she focuses on setting up interdisciplinary collaborations to develop multi-scale, multi-carrier, dynamic models that support system integration and decision-making across scale levels (technology-building-neighborhood-city-region-country) and sectors (mobility, industry, built environment). The evaluation of innovative technologies and their potential in addressing the key challenges of the energy transition is a priority.

In recent years, she's contributed to the development of the Climate Agreement of the Netherlands by developing 'the Renovation Accelerator', a subsidy program that was recently launched, aiming to accelerate the large-scale renovation of the housing stock. In this context, she's been an advisor and led research projects for multiple governmental organizations in the Netherlands. In addition to working for governmental organizations, she has built consortia with a wide variety of industry partners. Although she only recently was awarded her PhD thesis, she has already developed a substantial track record of publications and is already building teams of PDEngs, PhD's and postdocs on the topics 1) circularity/LCA, 2) sustainable renovation, 3) urban energy transition. She has been guest-editor for Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews and has authored publications for journals such as Building and Environment, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, Energy and Buildings and Journal of Cultural Heritage. She is a frequent reviewer for these and more academic journals and has been a member of several scientific committees of international conferences. She was chief editor (together with Emanuele Naboni) of the book publication 'Regenerative Design in Digital Practice'.

8:30 | **ZOOM OPEN**

9:00 | **OPENING**

Dr Michael Burnard, InnoRenew CoE
Deputy Director

9:05-9:35 | **KEYNOTE**

Lisanne Havinga, Assistant Professor,
Building Performance group,
Eindhoven University of Technology

9:35-11:05 | **ENGINEERING AND DESIGN**

9:35 Boris Azinović, Experimental investigations
of innovative seismic resistant CLT
connections

9:50 Igor Gavrić, Hybrid timber-steel shear wall
system for multi-story modular construction

10:05 Urban Kavka, Collecting Wood Waste
Generated During Construction of InnoRenew
CoE Building in Izola

10:20 Uroš Gantar, Near zero waste energy
window – wooden window for reuse and
cascading use

10:35 Mika Keskisalo, Form factor for efficient
low carbon construction

10:50 Laetitia Marrot, Developing electrically
conductive materials through thermal
conversions of hemp stalk wastes

11:05-11:30 | **COFFE BREAK**

11:30-12:30 | **CULTURAL HERITAGE**

11:30 Janez Kosel, Growth of xerophilic fungi on
model paint samples on glass and wooden
supports under low humidity conditions

11:45 Ana Slavec, Social mechanisms to engage
visitors in cultural heritage monuments
preservation

12:00 Tim Mavrič, Towards a common
framework for wood architectural heritage
conservation in Slovenia – a preparatory
overview

12:15 Veronika Kotradyova, Evaluation of
Residential Buildings Adaptation their
Interiors in a Rural Environment with a Deeper
Interdisciplinary Analysis of 3 Localities in
Slovakia

12:30-14:00 | **LUNCH**

14:00-15:15 | **HEALTH AND WELL-BEING**

14:00 Henrik Heräjärvi, Dependence of virgin
and recycled Scots pine heart- and sapwood
VOC emissions on indoor relative humidity
conditions

14:15 Mateja Erce, User needs and perspectives
on technologies or healthy ageing

14:30 Mark Dewsbury, Unhealthy advances in
Australian building regulations

14:45 Sabina Jordan, Temperature-based
approach for assessing buildings in terms of
providing thermal comfort for occupants

15:00 Nastja Podrekar Loredan, Development of
the School furniture suitability questionnaire
(SFS-Q)

15:15-15:30 | **COFFE BREAK**

15:30-16:15 | **MIXED TOPICS - FULL
PRESENTATIONS**

15:30 Lea Primožič, Three-pillar paradigm of
sustainability and its communication in the
wood industry – IKEA Group case study

15:45 Jan Vcelak, Prevention of mold formation
based on continuous condition monitoring of
timber constructions

16:00 Dennis Jones, The application of bicine or
tricine for limiting termite attack of thermally
modified wood

16:15 | **CLOSING**

11. 6. 2021

8:30 | **ZOOM OPEN**

9:00 | **OPENING**

Dr Michael Burnard, InnoRenew CoE
Deputy Director

9:05-10:20 | **MIXED TOPICS - SHORT PRESENTATIONS**

9:05 Filip Majstorović, Strengthening of flax textile-reinforced cement-based composite materials by the addition of pozzolans

9:10 Viktor Bukovszki, Smart contract affordances for energy communities

9:15 Petra Horvat, Relevant knowledge management approaches in the civil engineering research organizations and short overview of current situation in selected Slovenian public research organizations

9:20 Anja Jutraz, Renovation of outdoor school environment to ensure healthy environment for pupils

9:25 Lei Han, Creep Behaviour of Densified Wood

9:30 Tamás Storc, ANN Supporting EDS Building Optimisation

9:35 Kaja Kastelic, Assessing spinal posture while back supported sitting: a review of techniques used

9:40 Sidra Aslam, Mutable and Privacy-aware Decentralized Ledger for Data Management in Wood Supply Chain Environments

9:45 Esakkiammal Sudha Esakkimuthu, Optimization of polyphenols extraction from spruce bark

9:50 Ozlem Ozcenc, Increasing The Weathering Durability of The Wood Surface with Tree Bark Extractive Solution

9:55 Kelly Peeters, Extraction of phenolic compounds to determine its concentration in olive mill waste water

10:00 Vesna Starman, Education for a Sustainable Future

10:05 Erwin M. Schau, Metrics for LCA and carbon footprint of bio-based materials and processes: New indicators and normalisation factors for EN15804

10:10 Luca Versino, Perspectives of wood-based products for acoustic purposes in building

10:15 Václav Sebera, Electric guitar neck from densified poplar? Experimental and numerical analysis

10:20-10:50 | **COFFE BREAK**

10:50-12:05 | **INFORMATION AND COMPUTING TECHNOLOGY**

10:50 Richard Acquah, BIM Based Simulation Of Fire And Smoke Spread In Timber Buildings

11:05 Zsolt Ercsey, Sensitivity Analysis Supporting Building Optimisation

11:20 Kristóf Roland Horváth, Simulation Database Development Supporting Building Optimisation

11:35 Adam Katona, Evaluation and optimization of different wind tower geometries for passive air conduction systems with CFD simulations

11:50 Sebastjan Meža, Circular Economy And BIM In Civil Engineering

12:05 | **CLOSING**

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Mixed Topics - Short Presentations

Extraction of phenolic compounds to determine its concentration in olive mill wastewater

Kelly Peeters^{1,2}, Ana Miklavčič Višnjevec^{1,2,3}, Esakkiammal S. Essakimuthu¹, Črtomir Tavzes^{1,2}, Matthew J. Schwarzkopf^{1,2}

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Olive oil is the principal fat source of the traditional Mediterranean diet and due to its high content of polyphenols, has been credited with numerous human health benefits. The traditional olive pressing and the three phases continuous systems produce three streams: olive oil, olive pomace, and olive mill wastewater (OMWW). OMWW is known to be one of the most polluting effluents produced by the agro-food industries (Azaizeh, 2012). It exhibits high toxicity towards plants, bacteria, and aquatic organisms due to its composition of organic substances and phenolic compounds (Kalogerakis, 2013).

Our research aims to use this rich source of natural antioxidant phenolic compounds, present in OMWW, as basic ingredients in other industries (e.g. food supplements, food additives, beauty products). Before finding a method to separate the phenolic compounds from the OMWW, it is important to know the phenolic profile inside the OMWW because the phenolic content can vary greatly based on the genetic and environmental factors of the olives. Analysis of biophenols in OMWW generally parallels that for phenols from other sources, and a variety of procedures have been reported. Most rely on maximizing the recovery of one compound, hydroxytyrosol, and thus the complexity of the phenolic compounds may be underrepresented.

Several extraction techniques (ethyl acetate liquid-liquid extraction, filtration, liophilization with methanol extraction, use of enzymes, ultrasonification, acidification) were compared and evaluated on the recovery of forty-five different phenolic compounds. Phenolic compounds were characterized using a high-pressure liquid chromatography system with a diode array detector interfaced with a qTOF mass spectrometer (HPLC-DAD-ESI-QTOF). It was found that the ethyl acetate extraction technique, which is most commonly used, performed poorly in comparison with a technique using liophilization followed by methanol extraction.

Keywords: extraction techniques, HPLC-DAD-ESI-QTOF, olive mill wastewater, phenolic compounds

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- Azaizeh, H., Halahlh, F., Najami, N., Brunner, D., Faulstich, M., Tafesh, A., 2012. Antioxidant activity of phenolic fractions in olive mill wastewater. *Food Chem* 134, 2226–2234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2012.04.035>
- Kalogerakis N., Politi M., Foteinis S., Chatzisyneon E., and Mantzavinos D., 2013. Recovery of antioxidants from olive mill waste waters: a viable solution that promotes their overall sustainable management. *J Environ Manage*, 128, 749–758. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2013.06.027>